

Analysis Financial Performance of PT. Hensel Davest Indonesia, Tbk. Before and After the Initial Public Offering

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Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

Fintech, becoming a hot topic of discussion. *Fintech* itself has recently become a topic of conversation because it is a new phenomenon in the economic field that provides excellent opportunities. Due to this, many new *Fintech start-ups* have risen in popularity in Indonesia.

Apart from the excellent opportunities, *Fintech companies'* conveniences are why people are interested in starting a business in this field. *The National Digital Research Center* defines *Fintech* as *innovation in financial services* (Ardela, 2017).

ABSTRACT

Financial performance is one of the most important instrument to overlook a company's financial condition in a certain period of time. This research analyzes and compares the financial performance of PT. Hensel Davest Indonesia, Tbk. before and after Initial Public Offering. The method used in this research is a descriptive analysis method. Financial data is processed using financial ratio analysis. Meanwhile, financial performance comparison was conducted using non-parametric statistical methods of different tests or usually known as Wilcoxon. The result shows differences on PT. Hensel Davest Indonesia, Tbk financial performance before and after conducting Initial Public Offering. This difference is shown by the increasing and decreasing financial ratio before and after Initial Public Offering. This is supported by the results of statistical tests that show differences in financial performance before and after the Initial Public Offering. PT. Hensel Davest Indonesia, Tbk is expected to immediately evaluate and supervise the company's financial performance on a regular basis.

Keywords: FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE, INITIAL PUBLIC OFFERING

Introduction

The financial services industry is experiencing a massively significant innovation in line with today's rapid development of digital technology. Innovation in financial services is influenced by recent technological developments, with *Financial Technology*, which will be referred to as

The *Fintech* concept that adapts technological developments combined with the financial sector is expected to present more practical, safe, and modern financial transaction processes. Many things can be categorized into the *Fintech* field, including payment processes, transfers, buying and selling shares, *peer-to-peer* lending processes, and many more. When discussing buying and selling shares, PT. Hensel Davest Indonesia Tbk has just listed its shares on the Indonesia Stock Exchange through an *Initial Public Offering*, better known as an IPO (Intan & Rizqa, 2019). This company is engaged in developing trading applications via the internet (e-commerce) and distributing digital products and is the first Fintech company to be listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange. PT Hensel Davest Indonesia Tbk is predicted to reap fresh funds worth a total of Rp 38.11 billion.

Literature Review

Financial Technology

Fintech is used to describe new technologies that seek to improve and automate the delivery and use of financial services. At its core, Fintech helps companies, business owners, and consumers better manage their financial operations, processes, and lives by using specialized software and algorithms used on computers and smartphones (Kagan, 2019).

Bank Indonesia states that Fintech can replace the role of formal financial institutions such as banks. In terms of payment systems, Fintech plays a role in (Bank Indonesia, 2013):

1. Providing a market for business actors
2. Become a tool for payment, settlement, and clearing
3. Helping to make investments more efficient
4. Mitigation of risks from conventional payment systems
5. Helping those in need to save, borrow funds and invest in capital.

Investment

Investment is the act of allocating funds to assets or providing capital for a venture (business, project, real estate) with the hope of generating income or profit. In colloquial terms, investing also means putting time or effort, not just money, into something with long-term benefits, such as education. (Picardo, 2019). For some companies, investing activities are an essential element of the company's operations. An assessment of the company's performance may depend largely or entirely on the reported results of these activities. Some companies invest to allocate their excess funds, while others strengthen business relationships or obtain a trading advantage. From the information obtained, in general, investment objectives are as follows (Mudjijono, 2012):

1. To obtain fixed income in each period, such as interest, royalties, dividends, or rent, and others
2. To establish a special fund, for example, funds for expansion purposes and social interests
3. To control another company, through the ownership of a portion of the equity of that company

4. To ensure the availability of raw materials and obtain a market for the products produced
5. To reduce competition among similar companies
6. To maintain the relationship between companies.

Initial Public Offering

Initial Public Offering (IPO) refers to the process of offering a company's shares to the public in the issuance of new shares. Issuance of shares allows companies to raise capital from investors. The transition to being a public company can be a critical time for investors to analyze and invest in the company (Hayes, 2020).

A public offering is the sale of equity shares or other financial instruments to the masses for capital. Companies can use the raised capital to cover operational shortfalls, fund business expansion, or make strategic investments. Financial instruments offered to the public may include equity shares, such as common stock or preferred stock, or other tradable assets such as bonds (Chen, 2019).

Financial statements

According to Munawir (Munawir, 2014), the definition of financial statements comes from an accounting process that can be used to communicate between financial data or activities of a company and parties with interest in the data or activities of the company. The data present in the financial statements are income statements, balance sheets, changes in capital and cash flow statements. Meanwhile, a company's activities consist of making web or products, marketing the company's products or services, performing *maintenance* on the machines or applications the company uses.

Financial statements are also the management's responsibility for using the resources entrusted to them. The financial statements present information about the entity, which includes:

1. Assets
2. Liabilities
3. Equities
4. Advantages and disadvantages
5. Contribution from the owner as his capacity as owner
6. Cash flow.

Financial Performance Measurement

Financial performance is a subjective measure of how well a company can use the assets of its primary mode of business and generate revenue. Businesses also use this term as a general measure of their overall financial health over a given period. There are many ways to measure financial performance, but all steps must be taken in aggregate (Kenton, 2020).

One way to measure financial performance is by using ratio analysis. Ratio analysis is a quantitative method

to obtain information about a company's liquidity, operational efficiency, and profitability by studying its financial statements, such as balance sheets and income statements. Investors and analysts use ratio analysis to evaluate a company's financial health by examining past and current financial statements.

Comparative data can show the company's performance over time and can be used to estimate possible future performance. This data can also compare the company's financial position with the industry average while measuring how the company is dealing with others in the same sector (Bloomenthal, 2020).

Liquidity Ratio

The Liquidity Ratio measures the company's ability to meet its short-term debt obligations as they mature. This ratio measures the company's ability to pay off its short-term obligations as they fall due. Essentially, this liquidity ratio results from dividing cash and other current assets by short-term loans and current liabilities. This ratio shows how often short-term debt obligations can be covered by cash and other current assets (Kenton & Hayes, 2019).

a. Current Ratio

A *Current Ratio* measures the company's ability to pay off its current liabilities (paid in one year) with current assets such as cash, receivables, and inventories. The higher the ratio, the better the company's liquidity position. (Seth, 2019)

$$\text{Current Ratio} = \frac{\text{Current Assets}}{\text{Current Liabilities}}$$

b. Quick Ratio

A *Quick Ratio* measures the company's ability to meet its short-term obligations with its most liquid assets and, therefore, does not include current assets inventory. (Kenton, 2019)

$$\text{Quick ratio} = \frac{\text{current assets} - \text{inventory}}{\text{current liabilities}}$$

Activity Ratio

An *Activity Ratio* is a category of financial ratios that measure a company's ability to convert different accounts on its balance sheet into cash or sales. The activity ratio measures the relative efficiency of a company based on the use of assets, leverage, or other similar balance sheet items. It is essential in determining whether the company's management is doing a relatively good job of generating revenue and money from its resources (Klenton, 2019). The activity ratio can be divided into inventory turnover, average collection period, and total assets turnover.

a. Inventory Turnover

Inventory Turnovers measure the level of activity of the company stock (inventory) of the company.

$$\frac{\text{cost of good sold}}{\text{inventory}}$$

b. Average Collection Period

The *Average Collection Period* is the time it takes for a business to receive payments owed by a client in terms of accounts receivable (AR). Companies calculate the average collection period to ensure they have enough cash to meet their financial obligations.

$$ACP = \frac{\text{account receivables}}{\frac{\text{annual sales}}{365}}$$

c. Total Assets Turnover

Total Assets Turnover is a ratio that measures the efficiency of using company assets on product sales. In other words, the Total Assets Turnover Ratio is a measurement of a company's ability to generate sales from its total assets by comparing net sales with average total assets.

$$\text{Total asset turnover (TATO)} = \frac{\text{net sales}}{\text{average total assets}}$$

Debt Ratio

The debt ratio is used to measure how much a company relies on debt to finance its assets. This ratio can show the proportion of a company's debt to its total assets. Investors can use this debt ratio to determine how much debt the company has compared to its assets. Creditors can also measure how high the risk is given to a company (Kho, 2017).

a. Debt Ratio

A *Debt Ratio* is a financial ratio that measures the level of leverage of the company. The debt ratio is defined as total debt to total assets, expressed as a decimal or percentage. This can be interpreted as the proportion of company assets financed by debt.

$$\text{Debt ratio} = \frac{\text{total debt}}{\text{total assets}}$$

b. Times Interest Earned Ratio

Times Interest Earned Ratio can measure the company's ability to make interest payments. The higher the value, the greater the ability to pay its obligations.

$$\text{Times Interest Earned Ratio} = \frac{EBIT}{\text{Taxes}}$$

Profitability Ratio

A profitability ratio is a ratio used to assess a business' ability to generate revenue relative to its revenues,

operating costs, balance sheet assets, and equity over time, using data from a specific point in time. This ratio is essential for attracting investors who will invest in a company (Kenton, 2020).

a. *Gross Profit Margin*

Gross Profit Margin is a profitability measure that shows the percentage of revenue that exceeds the cost of goods sold (COGS). Gross profit margin reflects how successful a company's executive management team is in generating revenue, given the costs involved in producing their products and services. (Beers, 2019).

$$\text{Gross Profit Margin} = \frac{\text{Sales} - \text{COGS}}{\text{Sales}} \times 100\%$$

b. *Operating Profit Margin*

Operating profit margin measures the profit level from a company's operational activities against its sales. This means that the higher the *operating profit margin*, the better.

$$\text{Operating profit margin} = \frac{\text{operating profits}}{\text{sales}}$$

c. *Net Profit Margin*

Net profit margin measures the company's net profit level received on sales without considering fees, interest, expenses, taxes, and preferred stock dividends. This also means that the higher the net profit margin, the better.

$$\text{Net profit margin} = \frac{\text{earning available for common stock holders}}{\text{sales}}$$

d. *Earnings per Share*

EPS measures the company's rate of return on the *common stock* or *common stock* issued. EPS represents the amount of money generated during a specific period on several shares issued by the company (Nickolas, 2020).

$$\text{EPS} = \frac{\text{earning available for common stockholder}}{\text{number of shares of common stock outstanding}}$$

e. *Return on Assets*

ROA is an indicator of how profitable a company is relative to its total assets. ROA gives managers, investors, or analysts an idea of how efficiently a company's management uses its assets to generate revenue. Return on assets is shown as a percentage. (Fuhrmann, 2019)

$$\text{ROA} = \frac{\text{earnings available for common stockholders}}{\text{Total Asset}}$$

f. Return on Equity

Return on equity (ROE) is a measure of financial performance calculated by dividing net income by shareholder equity. Since equity is equal to company assets minus debt, ROE is considered a return on net assets. ROE also measures how effectively management uses company assets to generate profits. (Fuhrmann, 2019)

$$ROE = \frac{\text{earnings available for common stockholders}}{\text{common stock equity}}$$

Methodology

Types of research

The type of research conducted by the author includes quantitative research. According to Sugiyono (2013), quantitative research can be interpreted as a research method based on the philosophy of positivism. He also explained that quantitative research could examine specific populations or samples, where sampling techniques are generally carried out randomly, data collection uses research instruments, and quantitative data analysis to test the hypotheses applied. The population in this study is the financial statements of PT. Hensel Davest Indonesia, Tbk for a specific period (2018-2019). The sample in this study is the financial statements of PT. Hensel Davest Indonesia, Tbk for a certain period (2018-2019).

Research methods

According to Sugiyono, research methods are a scientific way to obtain data with specific goals and uses. Furthermore, appropriate methods are needed to achieve the required goals (Sugiyono, 2016). Based on this theory, a research method is a science of conducting research, from looking for actual data and facts to producing valid scientific reports. The research conducted by the author is included in the analytical descriptive research method that seeks to answer specific questions related to the topic being studied.

Data collection technique

The data collection technique used by the author is secondary data originating from various sources. The data used from secondary data are:

1. The financial statements of the company PT. Hensel Davest Indonesia Tbk period 2018-2019.
2. Information regarding the company's operating activities is obtained through literature studies, internet articles, television, and other publications.

Variable Operations

Table 1. Variable Operationalization

Variable	Method	Indicator	Scale
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Financial Performance	Liquidity Ratio	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Current Ratio - Quick Ratio 	Ratio
	Activity Ratio	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Inventory Turnover - Average Collection Period - Total Assets Turnover 	
	Debt Ratio	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Debt Ratio - Time Interest Earned Ratio 	
	Profitability Ratio	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Gross Profit Margin - Operating Profit Margin - Net Profit Margin - Earning per Share <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ROA - ROE 	

Data analysis technique

Data analysis was carried out using descriptive analysis techniques. Descriptive analysis is the interpretation of historical data to understand better the changes that have occurred in the business. Descriptive analytics describes the use of various historical data to draw comparisons. The most frequently reported financial data in descriptive analytics is, for example, year-over-year price changes, month-on-month sales growth, number of users, or total revenue per customer. These measures describe what has happened in the business over a certain period (Frankenfield, 2019).

Data analysis was carried out by comparing the calculation results of financial ratios with the company's available time-series data before and after the IPO. The results of this analysis are then interpreted to compare the performance.

Tests conducted by the author to help process the existing data, namely:

1. Statistical test

Statistical tests experiment on hypotheses by measuring and examining a random sample of the analyzed population. All analysts used a random population sample to test two different hypotheses: the null hypothesis and the alternative hypothesis. (Majaski, 2020).

2. Difference Test

The T-test is a type of inferential statistic used to determine whether there is a significant difference between the means of two groups, which may be related to certain features. It is mostly used when a data set, such as a data set recorded as flipping a coin 100 times, will follow a normal distribution and may have unknown variances. The t-test is used as a hypothesis testing tool, which allows testing assumptions that apply to a

population. (Kenton, 2020)

Table 2. Statistical Analysis

Problem	Hyphothesis	Statistic Test
Is there a difference in the company's financial performance before and after the IPO?	There is a difference in the company's financial performance before and after the IPO	- Data Normality Test - Different Test

Analysis

Financial Performance Analysis Before and After IPO (2018-2019)

Liquidity Ratio Analysis

a. Current Ratio

Table 3. Current Ratio of PT. Hensel Davest Indonesia

Ratio	2018	2019
Current Assets	81.502.260.755	273.017.186.353
Current Liabilities	34.247.673.291	8.138.489.361
Current Ratio	2.38	33.55

Source: Processed Data, 2020

In 2019, the company managed to record the total current assets of Rp.273 billion, a significant increase from the previous year at Rp. 191.5 billion or 334.98% compared to the value in 2018 of Rp. 81 billion. This occurred due to a decrease in prepaid expenses by 85.42%, a 100% increase in receivables and inventories, and 36.34% from IPO funds. All those increases combined caused current assets to increase in 2018.

In 2019, the company managed to record total current liabilities of IDR 8.1 billion, a decrease of IDR 26.1 billion or -76.24% compared to the value in 2018 of IDR 34.2 billion. The decrease was mainly due to making bank loans and taxes payable payments. This makes the *current ratio* increase to 33.55 in 2019.

b. Quick Ratio

Table 4. Quick Ratio PT. Hensel Davest Indonesia

Ratio	2018	2019
Current Assets	81.502.260.755	273.017.186.353
Inventory	71.680.667.026	97.732.426.555
Current Liabilities	34.247.673.291	8.138.489.361
Quick Ratio	0.29	21.54

Source: Processed Data, 2020

In line with the increase in *current assets*, inventories also experienced an increase of 36.34%, from Rp 71 billion to Rp 97 billion. With the increase in *current assets*, *inventory*, and decreasing *current liabilities*, the company's *quick ratio* increased to 21.54 in 2019.

Activity Ratio Analysis

a. Inventory Turnover

Table 5. Inventory Turnover PT. Hensel Davest Indonesia

Ratio	2018	2019
COGS	5.978.006.085.018	9.602.407.572.204
Inventory	71.680.667.026	97.732.426.555
Inventory Turnover	83.40	98.25

Source: Data processed, 2020

In 2019 after conducting the IPO, the company experienced an increase in the company's direct costs by increasing the company's *inventory* (prepaid PLN, postpaid PLN, non-tag listed PLN) and making *inventory turnover* increase to 98.25, which was initially only 83.40. This can also be seen from production activities which increased from 2018 to 2019 by 3,724,401,487,286.

b. Average Collection Period

Table 6. Average Collection Period of PT. Hensel Davest Indonesia

Ratio	2018	2019
Account receivable	87.865.337.134	166.300.818.548
Revenue	6.003.378.823. 540	9.629.824.866.769
Day in a year	365	365
Average Collection Period	5.34	6.30

Source: Processed Data, 2020

The company recorded revenue in 2019 of IDR 9 trillion, an increase of IDR 3 trillion or 60.41% compared to the total revenue in 2018 of IDR 6 trillion. The main factor for the increase in business segment revenue in 2019 was, among others, the increase in sales of PLN Prepaid products in 2019, which was Rp. 9 trillion, an increase of Rp. 3 trillion compared to 2018 of Rp. 5 trillion.

In 2019, there was an increase in the *average collection period* ratio because of increased revenue from 2018 to 2019 of Rp 3,626,446,043,229. Although there was a significant increase in trade receivables from third parties and other receivables, they were still below the revenue in 2019. Therefore, the average collection period ratio increased to 6.30 in 2019.

c. Total Asset Turnover

Table 7. Total Asset Turnover of PT. Hensel Davest Indonesia

Ratio	2018	2019
Revenue	6.003.378.823. 540	9.629.824.866.769
Total Asset	184.397.236.261	360.838.165.305

Total Asset Turnover	32.56	26.69
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Source: Data processed, 2020

In 2019, the company's total assets were recorded at Rp 360 billion, which consisted of 234.98% current assets and -13.06% non-current assets. The value of this total asset increased by Rp. 178 billion or 96.51% compared to 2018 of Rp. 184 billion. The increase in assets was due to an increase in inventories and accounts receivable due to IPO funds in 2019.

After conducting an IPO in 2019, the same amount of income and the number of assets increased, which helped to decrease the total asset turnover to 26.69 in 2019. Although there were an increased number of assets owned, the increase in income was much more significant. Furthermore, this is also because the increased assets have not been used so that they have not added to the company's operating income.

Debt Ratio Analysis

a. Debt Ratio

Table 8. Debt Ratio of PT. Hensel Davest Indonesia

Ratio	2018	2019
Total Liabilities	34.884.550.334	8.240.423.892
Total Asset	184.397.236.261	360.838.165.305
Debt Ratio	18.91	2.28

Source: Data processed, 2020

In 2019 there was a decrease in the *debt ratio* from 18.91 to 2.28. This decrease was because the number of assets increased by 96.51%. Meanwhile, the amount of debt to be paid was decreased by 71.51%. This also occurred because tax debts and non-trade payables experienced a significant decrease. Thus, the amount of debt that decreased rapidly, while the number of assets experienced an upturn, made the *debt ratio* decrease in 2019.

b. Time Interest Earned Ratio

Table 9. Time Interest Earned Ratio of PT. Hensel Davest Indonesia

Ratio	2018	2019
EBT	15.136.543.635	15.004.428.688
Tax	3.797.209.705	3.172.508.866
Time Interest Earned Ratio	3.99	4.73

Source: Processed Data, 2020

Although profit before tax decreased from 15,136,543,635 to 15,004,428,688, the *time interest earned ratio* increased. This occurred because of a decrease in taxes, allowing the company to pay future interest expenses.

Profitability Ratio Analysis

a. Gross Profit Margin

Table 10. Gross Profit Margin of PT. Hensel Davest Indonesia

Ratio	2018	2019
Gross Profit	25.372.738.522	27.417.294.565
Revenue	6.003.378.823.540	9.629.824.866.769
Gross Profit Margin	0.42	0.28

Source: Processed Data, 2020

The *gross profit margin* ratio decreased because although there was an increase in gross profit, the figure was still far too insignificant compared to the company's revenue. Due to this, the *gross profit margin* ratio declined in 2019.

b. Operating Profit Margin

Table 11. Operating Profit Margin of PT. Hensel Davest Indonesia

Ratio	2018	2019
Operating Profit	14.557.214.281	10.628.506.397
Revenue	6.003.378.823.540	9.629.824.866.769
Operating Profit Margin	0.24	0.11

Source: Processed Data, 2020

The decrease in the *operating profit margin* ratio was due to increased company expenses, such as general and administrative expenses, interest expenses, and other expenses. So this makes the operating profit margin ratio experience a decrease from 0.24 to 0.11 in 2019.

c. Net Profit Margin

Table 12. Net Profit Margin of PT. Hensel Davest Indonesia

Ratio	2018	2019
Earning available for common stockholders	11.339.333.931	11.831.919.822
Revenue	6.003.378.823.540	9.629.824.866.769
Net Profit Margin	0.18	0.12

Source: Processed Data, 2020

The decrease in the *net profit margin* ratio from 2018 of 0.18 to 0.12 in 2019 occurred due to a relatively significant increase in sales, general, interest, and other expenses. Although the profit available to shareholders has increased, the company's expenses have also increased, and this has caused *the company's net profit margin* to decline in 2019.

d. Earning Per Share

Table 13. Earning Per Share PT. Hensel Davest Indonesia

Ratio	2018	2019
Earning available for common stockholders	11.339.333.931	11.831.919.822
Number of shares of common stockholders	828.650.000	1.083.831.869
Earning per Share	13.68	10.92

Source: Processed Data, 2020

This decrease in *earnings per share* occurred because shareholders increased by 1.9% while profits only increased by 1.04%. This made *earnings per share* in 2019 decrease to 10.92 from 13.68.

e. Return On Assets

Table 14. ROA of PT. Hensel Davest Indonesia

Ratio	2018	2019
Earning available for common stockholders	11.339.333.931	11.831.919.822
Total Assets	184.397.236.261	360.838.165.305
ROA	6.15	3.27

Source: Processed Data, 2020

Although the number of company assets increased from 2018 to 2019 from 184,397,236,261 to 360,838,165,305, shareholder profits increased from 11,339,333,931 to 11,831,919,822. This did not necessarily make the company's ROA increase, however. In contrast, it experienced a decrease to 3.27 after the IPO.

f. Return On Equity

Table 15. ROE of PT. Hensel Davest Indonesia

Ratio	2018	2019
Earning available for common stockholders	11.339.333.931	11.831.919.822
Common Stock Equity	149.512.685.927	352.597.741.413
ROE	7.58	3.36

Source: Processed data, 2020

Although shareholder profits have increased, ROE has decreased from 7.58 to 3.36 in 2019 after the IPO. This decreased the company's profitability due to the increasing expenses in 2019, making all profitability experience a decrease.

Table 16. Summary of Financial Ratios of PT. Hensel Davest Indonesia, Tbk (2018-2019)

Ratio / Year	2018 (Before)	2019 (After)	Description	Difference
Rasio Likuiditas				
Current Ratio	2.38	33.55	Increased	31.17
Quick Ratio	0.29	21.54	Increased	21.25
Rasio Aktivitas				
Inventory Turnover	83.40	98.25	Increased	14.85
Average Collection Period	5.34	6.30	Increased	0.96
Total Asset Turnover	32.56	26.69	Decreased	-5.87
Rasio Hutang				
Debt Ratio	18.91	2.28	Decreased	-16.63
Time Interest Earned Ratio	3.99	4.73	Increased	0.74
Rasio Profitabilitas				
Gross Profit Margin	0.42	0.28	Decreased	-0.14
Operating Profit Margin	0.24	0.11	Decreased	-0.13
Net Profit Margin	0.18	0.12	Decreased	-0.06
Earning Per Share	13.68	10.92	Decreased	-2.76
ROA	6.15	3.27	Decreased	-2.88
ROE	7.58	3.36	Decreased	-4.22

Source: Processed data, 2020

Statistical analysis

The author used a difference test to perform the statistical analysis of the financial performance of PT. Hensel Davest Indonesia Tbk before and after conducting the IPO. The analysis results presented were the results of data processed using the SPSS program.

Figure 1. Average Financial Ratio of PT. Hensel Davest Indonesia, Tbk Before and After IPO

Source: Data processed, 2020

The graph above illustrates the average value of all Hensel Davest Indonesia's financial ratios from before and after the IPO. Before the IPO, the lowest average figure was Net Profit Margin of 0.18, while the highest average was Inventory Turnover, 83.40. Then after the IPO, the lowest average figure was the Operating Profit Margin of 0.11, while the highest average number was Inventory Turnover which is 98.25. Furthermore, the most significant difference in the company's financial ratios before and after the IPO, based on table 5.14, is the Current Ratio of 31.17.

Difference Test Analysis

a. Normality Test Before and After

Ho: Data comes from a normally distributed population

H1: Data comes from a population that is not normally distributed

±= 5%

Test Criteria:

1. Accept Ho if P-Value (sig) > 0.05

2. Reject H0 if P-Value (sig) < 0.05

Table 17. Normality Test Before and After

		Tests of Normality					
		Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a			Shapiro-Wilk		
		Statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.
Before	2018	.293	13	.003	.621	13	.000
	2019	.275	13	.008	.634	13	.000

Source: Data processed, 2020

Based on the table above, the results of the normality test of financial ratio data before (2018) and after (2019) conducted an *initial public offering* (IPO) can be seen. Both data groups have P-Value(sig) of 0.000 and 0.000, respectively, less than 0.05. This means that the H_0 is rejected. It can be concluded that the company's financial ratio data before and after conducting an *initial public offering* (IPO) are not normally distributed.

b. Difference Test of Before and After

The author conducted this test to determine whether or not there are differences in the financial performance of PT. Hensel Davest Indonesia Tbk before and after conducting the IPO.

$\pm = 5\%$

Test Criteria:

1. P value is not significant if $P > 0.05$
2. P value is significant if $P < 0.05$

Table 18. Difference Test Before and After

		t/Z Count	P Value	Conclusion
Whole	2018	-0,105	0,917	There is a difference
	2019			

Source: Data processed, 2020

Figure 2. Hypothesis Test
Source: Data processed, 2020

The test was carried out using the Wilcoxon test, meaning the test results will be significant if the P-value < 0.05 . Before and after the IPO, the difference test results show that the calculated Z value is -0.105 with a P-value of 0.917. Because $P (0.917) < 0.05$, the P-value is significant. Thus, it can be concluded that there is a difference between the overall financial performance before and after carrying out the *initial public offering* (IPO). The result of the difference test before and after the IPO shows the Z count $-0.105 > t$ table - 2.160. Therefore, it can be concluded that there is a difference between before and after the company conducts the IPO. This overall difference occurs because the ratio increases, and there is also a decrease. However, the

most significant can be seen from the profitability ratios where all of its elements have decreased, even though the profitability ratio is essential in seeing the company succeed in making a profit or losing. If the company cannot make a profit, then the company cannot be said to be *bona fide*, making the investors lose interest in the company. It can be said that the financial ratios of PT. Hensel Davest Indonesia, Tbk is still not adequate compared to similar industries.

Conclusion

After conducting the IPO, the financial performance of PT. Hensel Davest Indonesia tends to decline more than before the IPO. Financial ratios that have decreased are *total asset turnover*, *debt ratio*, *gross profit margin*, *operating profit margin*, *net profit margin*, *earnings per share*, *return on assets*, and *equity*. Meanwhile, the only ratios that experienced an increase were the *current ratio*, *quick ratio*, *inventory turnover*, *average collection period*, and *time interest earned ratio*. Statistical tests conducted using the company's financial ratio data show that there were differences in the financial performance of PT. Hensel Davest Indonesia, Tbk before and after conducting the IPO.

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